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***Brachyta bifasciata* (Olivier, 1795) - protected name
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract: *Brachyta bifasciata* (Olivier, 1795) (not *Leptura bifasciata* O.F. Müller, 1776) is declared as a protected name because of prevailing usage according to the Art. 23.9. of ICZN (1999). More than 25 works, published by more than 10 authors in preceding 50 years are listed.

Common name *Brachyta bifasciata* (Olivier, 1795) originally introduced as *Leptura bifasciata* Olivier, 1795 is well known as a junior homonym (not *Leptura bifasciata* O.F. Müller, 1776) - Art. 53.3 - Danilevsky (2020: 155). The name must be protected according to the prevailing usage (Art. 23.9. of ICZN 1999). The junior homonym has been used for a particular taxon, as its presumed valid name, in at least 25 works, published by at least 10 authors in the immediately preceding 50 years and encompassing a span of not less than 10 years.

More than 25 works, published by more than 10 authors in preceding 50 years are:

Agafonova et al. (2022), Anisimov & Bezborodov (2020), Chiang & Chen (2001), Danilevsky (2010, 2014, 2020), Hayashi (1980), Hua (2002), Hwang (2015), Jang et al. (2015), Jałoszyński et al. (2014), Korsun et al. (2012), Lin & Yang (2019), Lobanov et al. (1981), Löbl & Smetana (2010), Ohbayashi (1984, 2007), Ohbayashi et al. (1992), Švácha (1989), Smirnov (2009), Tsherepanov (1979, 1988, 1990, 1996), Tshernyshev & Dubatolov (2005), Wang (2003, 2014), Wang et al. (2012), Xu & Neng (2010), Xu et al. (2007).

M.A. Lazarev

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M.A. Lazarev

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